

Incidence of emerging *Candida auris* infection in Bangladesh: A rapid review of the literature

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Abstract

Introduction: Global environmental changes, including rising atmospheric temperatures due to climate variability, are increasingly linked to the emergence or resurgence of fungal infections worldwide. *Candida auris* (*C. auris*) is a notable example, with studies suggesting that heat stress may prompt genetic adaptations in these fungi, facilitating their environmental resilience. This study reviews the existing knowledge and clinical impact of emerging *C. auris* infections in Bangladesh. It underscores the importance of evidence-based research in shaping policies for early detection and enhanced preparedness for potential outbreaks.

Methods: Between November 1st and December 31st, 2023, we conducted a rapid review of the scientific literature focusing on *C. auris*, antibiotic resistance, fungal disease, Bangladesh, and climate change. This involved systematic searches of databases like Google Scholar, MEDLINE (PubMed), and Web of Science, as well as grey literature and relevant websites like the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Center for Disease Control (CDC), with a narrative synthesis of studies in English that addressed the incidence of *C. auris* infections and their antibiotic susceptibility in Bangladesh, excluding non-primary research such as protocols, reviews, dissertations, and posters.

Results: Our review synthesized four studies from hospitals in Dhaka and Mymensingh, Bangladesh, revealing the prevalence of *C. auris* infections, especially in neonates and adults in intensive care units. These studies primarily identified *C. auris* from blood and urine samples, with a significant concentration in neonatal intensive care units, and highlighted a persistent presence and resistance to antibiotics, particularly fluconazole. Antifungal susceptibility testing across these studies demonstrated varying resistance levels, notably high resistance to fluconazole and moderate resistance to other antifungals like amphotericin B and voriconazole.

Conclusions: Bangladesh's insufficient healthcare infrastructure, together with inappropriate use and overprescription of antibiotics, are significant causes of antibiotic resistance. More studies need to be undertaken on *C. auris* in Bangladesh and worldwide.

Take-home message: This rapid review highlights the urgent need for enhanced surveillance and targeted antifungal strategies in hospital settings to combat the growing prevalence and significant drug resistance of *C. auris* in Bangladesh.

Keywords: antibiotic resistance; Bangladesh; *Candida auris*; climate change

INTRODUCTION

Candida auris (*C. auris*), first recognized in 2009, has quickly emerged as a major health concern owing to its resistance to antifungal treatments and high mortality rates in outbreaks associated with healthcare settings [1]. This fungal pathogen is strongly influenced by climate change, so it has been defined as “the first human pathogenic fungus” that has emerged due to climate change. In their systematic review, Akinbobola et al. [2] studied the possible pathways through which *C. auris* can be introduced into the environment. They evaluated the environmental characteristics influencing its persistence and transmission in natural environments, including increased global temperatures [3,4].

C. auris is a globally distributed pathogenic yeast that can cause invasive candidiasis of the blood (candidemia), heart, central nervous system, eyes, bones, and internal organs. Invasive candidiasis is a severe nosocomial infection mainly affecting critically ill and immunocompromised patients [5]. *C. auris* is an emerging fungus that presents a serious global health threat. The isolation of *C. auris* in two locations in the Andaman Islands confirms that this fungus may thrive in specific environmental conditions. It indicates that clinical isolates may originate from the environment. The significance of survival in the wilderness lies in the fact that microbes encounter significant temperature variations, severe levels of humidity, and predation by other microbes like amoeba. Unlike in mammalian hosts, these conditions can favor the development of characteristics that enhance virulence [6]. *C. auris* exhibits a higher temperature tolerance than its closely related species and demonstrates greater resistance to hypersaline conditions than most *Candida* species [7]. Casadevall et al. have hypothesized that the origin of *C. auris* may be associated with climate change and global temperature fluctuations due to its thermotolerance [8]. *C. auris* lives on textiles, plastics, and other nonporous surfaces for weeks. *C. auris* infections are a global health problem due to resistance to antifungal treatments like fluconazole and amphotericin B.

Approximately 1.7 billion individuals worldwide are afflicted by a fungal infection, most manifesting as mucosal and superficial skin infections [9]. *C. auris*-associated invasive infections have a higher mortality rate than infections produced by other *Candida* species [10,11]. *C. auris* infections have a crude fatality rate ranging from 30% to 72%. It accounts for 9-13% of neonates' BSI (Bloodstream infection) [12]. Most *C. auris* strains resist one or more antifungal treatment classes, one-third to two classes, and some strains to all three main antifungal medicines. In medical institutions, *C. auris* can spread easily from patient to patient [13]. *C. auris*, a multidrug-resistant (MDR) fungus, was first identified in 2009 in a hospital in Japan from an isolate found in the external ear [14,15]. Candidemia is the predominant invasive fungal infection in affluent countries, i.e., Europe and the United States of America, leading to substantial expenses and accounting for 40% of hospital mortality [16]. Increasing data indicates probable transmission of *C. auris* in healthcare settings. Between April 2015 and July 2016, a significant epidemic of 50 cases of *C. auris* occurred in a cardio-thoracic facility in London. The yeast was consistently found near bed-space regions [17].

C. auris is the sole fungal pathogen now classified as an urgent risk to health by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). This classification is typically reserved for bacteria that are resistant to drugs [18]. The World Health

Organisation (WHO) has recently placed *C. auris* on its “fungal pathogen priority list,” classifying it as a fungal pathogen of critical concern to direct research, development, and public health initiatives [5]. *C. auris* infections are opportunistic, similar to other *Candida* infections, and are particularly risky for individuals with underlying health issues such as diabetes, kidney disease, and HIV/AIDS. Risk factors also include prolonged use of antimicrobial drugs, extended hospital stays, surgeries, and the use of central venous catheters. Recently, COVID-19 has been identified as a potential risk factor for severe *C. auris* infections, given the high mortality rates observed among COVID-19 patients who acquire this infection [2].

Research has demonstrated that detecting *C. auris* infections early is advantageous, as it allows for administering suitable antifungal treatment, preserving numerous lives [18]. Nevertheless, the difficulty of promptly initiating therapy for *C. auris* persists due to the limited capacity of many commercially available identification systems/platforms to rapidly diagnose it.

Features of C. auris that increase the risk of co-infection

C. auris, unlike any other fungal disease, has quickly developed into an acutely alarming infectious agent, gaining pandemic dimensions and establishing its status as a superbug barely ten years after its initial isolation in 2009 [19,20]. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) have classified *C. auris* as an urgent health danger, the first and only fungal pathogen to do so [21]. In a recent study, *C. auris* was found to be the most prevalent causative agent of *Candida* bloodstream infections (candidemia) in a tertiary care multispecialty center in Western India, accounting for roughly 43% of all *Candida* isolates [22]. This finding highlights the potential for *C. auris* to become even more prominent in *Candida* infections.

Antifungal resistance is a critical trait shared by several strains of *C. auris*: 90% of the isolates are found to be resistant to at least one antifungal drug class, 30% to at least two different classes, and even pan-resistance isolates (isolates resistant to all antifungal classes currently used in clinics) have been described [23]. Easy transmission is a crucial characteristic of *C. auris*, contributing to its effectiveness as a global spreader [24]. Most infections caused by other members of the *Candida* family are endogenous in nature, while *C. auris* is regularly spread from person to person by direct or indirect contact [24]. Since *C. auris* appears highly adapted to thrive outside the human host, it is frequently isolated from human skin or the hospital surroundings [19,25]. *C. auris* has the most concerning traits, i.e., the propensity to attach to and stay on abiotic surfaces, including human skin, ears, and nasal canals, as well as dry and damp surfaces, bedding, floors, sinks, and beds [26-29].

Biofilm, a trait of fungal pathogens, is a mechanism through which microbes grow and irreversibly connect to surfaces, producing extracellular polymers that help in adhesion and matrix development [30]. The capacity of *C. auris* to successfully colonize and remain on human skin and disseminate easily among patients may be explained by the fact that it has been observed to produce high-burden, dense multilayer biofilms on the skin surface [31,32]. Another distinctive characteristic of *C. auris* is that it forms an aggregative phenotype that is the capacity to develop sizable aggregates or pseudohyphal-like cells, where mother and daughter cells remain linked to one another [24].

C. auris needs a weakened host immune system compared to other members of the *Candida* family [19,20]. Preexisting medical conditions like diabetes, kidney disease, and HIV/AIDS [20,33,34], as well as long-term use of antibiotics, prolonged hospital admissions, surgery, and the use of a central venous catheter, are all risk factors for *C. auris* infections [20,33].

Climate change and evolving fungal pathogens C. auris

Mammals are protected by a thermal restriction zone (TRZ) between their high basal temperatures and the surrounding temperatures [35]. The earth's climate has undergone significant changes throughout its history, with periods of globally temperate climate (glaciations) followed by warming [36,37]. Climate has significantly impacted human development, and agriculture and sedentary communities first appeared around the end of the last glacial period (around 12,500 years ago) [38,39]. These processes influence TRZ for most of the fungi. Thus TRZ no longer provides this natural antifungal barrier with the same efficacy due to climate change, which favors the adaptation of bacteria to higher temperatures [35].

Most fungi thrive in the range of 12°C to 30°C [40], while some grow at temperatures as low as -10°C [41] or as high as 65°C [42]. Mutations accelerated under heat stress, and the study found that after 800 generations of growth in a laboratory medium, fungus raised at body temperature (37°C) had a five-times greater rate of transposon mutations than fungi raised at 30°C [43]. Fungus of numerous species can thrive in ambient temperatures, while only a small proportion of species can reproduce at 37°C [40]. Compared to most of its closely related species, *C. auris* can thrive at higher temperatures and survive hypersaline settings better than most *Candida* species [29]. Rising temperature is one of the major factors in the adaptation of *C. auris*.

***C. auris* isolation from coastal habitat**

C. auris was isolated from a maritime habitat, specifically from a salt marsh and sand beach in India's Coastal Wetlands of the Andaman Islands [44]. This study reported that *C. auris* was surprisingly separated from two distinct environments, i.e., salt marsh wetland and sandy beach, which were both multidrug-susceptible and multidrug-resistant. The author confirmed by investigating whole-genome sequencing analysis that the isolated clusters of *C. auris* resembled species from South Asian clade I.

Identifying *C. auris* in Colombian estuaries adds to the evidence that this fungus existed in the environment before being identified as a human pathogen [45]. This study reported that since 2015, an unusually high number of *C. haemulonii* bloodstream infection cases were reported later. It was identified as *C. auris* and has been retroactively detected in clinical settings.

Candida auris, a nosocomial fungal pathogen first identified in 2009, has rapidly evolved into a critical health concern due to its resistance to multiple antifungal drugs and high mortality rates in healthcare-associated outbreaks. By 2019, it was classified as one of the top five urgent antimicrobial threats. The recent identification of a sixth clade (Clade VI) in Bangladesh [1], which poses a risk of international spread, underscores the urgent need for a comprehensive literature review. Against this backdrop, this rapid review is essential to understand this evolving threat better and equip policymakers with the necessary tools to effectively address this challenging public health issue. Therefore, our research aimed to study the incidence of *C. auris* infection and its susceptibility to antibiotics in Bangladesh.

METHODS

From November 1st to December 31st, 2023, a rapid review of the scientific literature was carried out. We searched electronic databases, such as Google Scholar, MEDLINE (PubMed), Web of Science, and grey literature sources. We also visited the WHO and CDC websites to get country-specific information. The studies written in English were included, and a narrative synthesis was undertaken. We conducted systematic searches with several keywords, including *C. auris*, antibiotic resistance, fungal disease, Bangladesh, and climate change.

Therefore, we adapted the PRISMA-S (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses literature search extension) statement for this rapid review, according to the methodology suggested by Klerings et al. [46].

We included articles written in English, with a geographic focus on Bangladesh, concerning the incidence of *C. auris* infection and its susceptibility to antibiotics. Protocols, reviews, dissertations, and poster presentations were all subject to exclusion criteria to ensure that only relevant primary research papers fulfilling the study's aims and geographic scope were chosen.

The quality assessment of studies was conducted using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) scales [48]. The appropriate tool was selected based on the type of study being evaluated. Each JBI tool includes four possible responses for all components: Yes, No, Unclear, or Not Applicable.

RESULTS

Our review included only 4 studies [45,49-51] conducted across various hospitals in Dhaka and Mymensingh, Bangladesh, showing the emergence and prevalence of *C. auris* infections, particularly in neonates and adults in intensive care units.

Figure 1 summarizes a rapid review search to identify published literature on the incidence of emerging *Candida auris* infection in Bangladesh [47].

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram of the included studies.

The studies reported on *C. auris* isolations predominantly from blood and urine samples in hospital settings, with most cases found in neonatal intensive care units (NICU).

Dutta et al. (2019) identified 21 cases of *C. auris*, with 66.7% from blood samples mainly in the ICU. Jalil et al. (2020) and subsequent studies in 2022 and 2023 by Sathi et al. showed a persistent presence and antibiotic resistance of *C. auris* in blood samples, noting particularly high resistance rates to fluconazole. Antifungal susceptibility tests revealed varying resistance across different drugs, including high resistance to fluconazole and moderate resistance to other antifungals such as amphotericin B and voriconazole.

In their landmark study, Dutta et al. (2019) [45] identified *C. auris* in 21 out of 100 clinical samples, highlighting its prevalence in Bangladesh. This study demonstrated notable antifungal resistance: 19% of samples showed resistance to amphotericin B using the Disk Diffusion Method (DDM), 23% through Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) tests, 66.7% to fluconazole by DDM, and 42.8% by MIC. Additionally, resistance to voriconazole was observed in 85% of samples across both testing methods.

Jalil et al. [49] further detailed resistance patterns in non-albicans *Candida* species. Of the 146 samples tested, 56 were positive, predominantly identifying *C. tropicalis*, *C. parapsilosis*, *C. auris*, and *C. dubliniensis*. This study found exceptionally high resistance rates to fluconazole (96.6%), ketoconazole (84.5%), itraconazole (13.8%), and clotrimazole (43.1%).

Expanding the scope, Sathi et al. [49] examined a larger cohort of 360 samples, finding 109 positives for *Candida*. This research highlighted a significant prevalence of fluconazole resistance, particularly in *C. cijferrii*, *C. auris*, and *K. ohmeri*, with resistance rates surpassing 67%. *C. krusei* displayed inherent resistance to fluconazole.

Tables 1 and 2 complement these findings by presenting the incidence of *C. auris* infections and the antifungal susceptibility of isolated pathogens in Bangladesh. The scores assigned to each study based on the quality assessment are provided in Table 1. None of the studies were excluded due to quality evaluation.

Table 1 Incidence of *C. auris* infection in Bangladesh.

Authors	Study sample	Study location	Main findings	Quality assessment	Reference
Dutta et al, 2019	Clinical samples included urine, blood, sputum, pus, high vaginal swab, and body fluid.	Patients admitted in wards, intensive care unit [ICU] and neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) in a hospital in Dhaka city	Out of 100 <i>Candida</i> sp. tested, 21 isolates were identified as <i>C. auris</i> . Of the 21 <i>C. auris</i> , 14 (66.7%) were isolated from blood samples and the remaining 7 (33.4%) were from urine. Most of the <i>C. auris</i> isolated were from patients admitted to intensive care units.	9/10	[45]
Jalil et al, 2020	Blood samples with clinical features of septicemia.	Four tertiary care hospitals of Dhaka city	<i>C. auris</i> (5.2%)	8/10	[49]
Sathi et al, 2022	High vaginal swabs (HVSs), blood, and aural swabs	Mymensingh Medical College Hospital	Three isolates from blood discharge were genetically identified as <i>C. auris</i>	10/10	[50]
Sathi et al, 2023	Blood and aural swabs (discharge) of patients with suspected candidemia and otomycosis	Mymensingh Medical College Hospital	Out of 22 isolates, n=5 was <i>C. auris</i> . Out of 18 isolates identified from septicemia, 7 were <i>C. auris</i> .	10/10	[51]

Table 2. Number of isolated pathogens according to the specimens and antifungal susceptibility.

Authors and year	Sample size	Sub-group (age, gender)	Specimen	Location	Incidence Number (%)	Susceptibility to antifungals: Methods include Disk Diffusion (DI) and Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)
Dutta et al, 2019 [45]	n=21	Adult	Blood	ICU	1 (5%)	Amphotericin B Fluconazole Voriconazole
				CCU	-	
			Urine	ICU	5 (24%)	
				CCU	1 (5%)	
				Ward	1 (5%)	
Neonate	Blood	NICU	13 (61.9%)			
Jalil et al, 2020 [49]	n=58	Neonate	Blood	NICU	3 (5.2%)	Fluconazole
Sathi et al, 2022 [50]	n=109	Neonate (15 day old)	Blood	NICU	3 (7.7%)	Fluconazole Itraconazole Amphotericin B Voriconazole
Sathi et al, 2023 [51]	n=22	Neonate (2-30 days)	Blood	NICU	5 (23%)	Amphotericin B Fluconazole

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to examine the current knowledge and conduct a situational analysis of the emerging *C. auris* infection in Bangladesh to inform policy agenda related to early detection and monitoring for outbreak preparedness. The results are discussed herewith. The results of this study highlighted the prevalence and resistance patterns of *C. auris* infections in Bangladesh, emphasizing the urgent need for effective strategies to address the growing burden of drug-resistant fungal infections. The findings show that *C. auris* is prevalent in numerous healthcare facilities and patient populations. Alarming rates of amphotericin B, fluconazole, and voriconazole resistance highlight the constraints of conventional treatment and the need for continuous surveillance.

Healthcare-associated infection, irrational use of antibiotics

Among fungi-caused nosocomial infections, candida infections are the most prevalent and are becoming a severe global public health issue. In contrast to non-*auris* candidemia, specific risk factors for developing *C. auris* infection include prolonged intensive care unit admission, prior antimicrobial therapy, placement of a central vascular catheter, administration of total parenteral nutrition (TPN), and the presence of underlying comorbidities like respiratory, neurological, or kidney disease [52-61].

Poor sanitation, cleanliness, water supply, and unsafe medical waste management in hospitals in Dhaka and other parts of Bangladesh all paint a bleak image of hygiene practices in Bangladesh [62]. During the COVID-19 pandemic, it was reported that household and communicable medical waste are increasing [63,64].

National service provision assessment has revealed that Bangladesh's healthcare facilities were severely lacking, with only 50% (the maximum score, 100%) of the necessary equipment and infrastructure for standard precautions for infection prevention accessible in all facilities [65]. Bangladesh is a significant contributor to antibiotic resistance due to its inadequate healthcare infrastructure, improper utilization, and excessive prescription of antibiotics [52]. Like other developing nations in Bangladesh, the irrational usage of antibiotics is a significant concern as it is driven by poor surveillance, limited knowledge, and a tendency among patients for self-medication [66]. The misuse of antibiotics has been significantly worsened because of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has contributed to the escalated prevalence of antibiotic resistance (ABR) [66].

Moreover, prolonged hospital stays, broad-spectrum antibiotics, or other invasive procedures can disrupt our body's normal balance of microorganisms. Thus, the environment is conducive to developing *C. auris* or other opportunistic infections. Studies found tuberculosis services were the least equipped of all service sectors and improperly implemented TB IPC measures in health settings [65,67].

Climate change dynamics

Bangladesh, a tropical monsoon nation in South Asia, is extremely susceptible to climate change-induced risks such as floods due to its distinctive geographical positioning, population density, pervasive poverty, and excessive reliance on natural resources. Bangladesh has experienced an average rise in temperature of 0.5°C between 1976 and 2019, and summers have become longer, winters have become warmer, and the monsoon has become more erratic than usual [68].

Due to its low-lying deltaic geography, Bangladesh is particularly vulnerable to soil and water salinization. Moreover, climate change has also played a significant role in the past 50 years in elevating soil and water salinization [69,70]. Evidence suggests that *C. auris* can adapt to higher temperatures and be isolated from salt marsh sediment and sandy wetland beaches. Compared to most *Candida* species, *C. auris* is more tolerant of hypersaline conditions [7,44]. Due to *C. auris*'s combination of salinity and heat tolerance, it can thrive in specialized ecosystems, such as wetlands [35].

The prevalence of *C. auris* infections presents a variety of complex issues, which, when combined with elements related to healthcare and the dynamics of climate change, highlights the urgent need for comprehensive solutions to address these new public health hazards in Bangladesh.

CONCLUSIONS

Future investigation is necessary to explore the pathway of *C. auris* in developing nations. Outside of this study, evidence shows no environmental exploration of *C. auris* exists. Current understanding may encourage the development of novel evidence regarding the ecological reservoirs of *C. auris* and the underlying mechanisms by which it transmits interspecies or through the environment. This study will provide invaluable insights that can inform and direct future initiatives in healthcare policy, surveillance, and antimicrobial stewardship that can lessen the consequences of *C. auris* infections and tackle the wider problem of antibiotic resistance. Given the persistent problems of antibiotic resistance and inadequate healthcare infrastructure in Bangladesh, the rise and prevalence of *C. auris* may exacerbate the nation's public health concerns. The significance of the interconnections among human, animal, and ecosystem health as determinants in the emergence and dissemination of novel fungal pathogenic species can be better comprehended through additional investigation into the research gaps.

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